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Determinants of Knowledge of Environmental Sanitation among Teachers in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to investigate age, marital status and level of education as determinants of knowledge of environmental sanitation among teachers in Obio/Akpor Local government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population for this study comprised of all teachers secondary schools (both public and private schools) within Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. A total of 450 respondents were selected to participate in this study using Taro Yamene's formula for sample selection. A self-structured questionnaire titled Determinants of knowledge of environmental sanitation questionnaire (DKESQ) was used. Descriptive statistical tools were used to answer research questions; One-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses. The results showed that the teachers in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State of 20 – 30 years have high knowledge of environmental sanitation. The findings also revealed that the male teachers in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State have high knowledge of environmental sanitation, and there was no significant difference in knowledge of environmental sanitation among teachers in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State based on age, gender, and level of education. The study recommended that environmental experts should be brought to the schools once in a while to mount workshops or seminars on school sanitation. This will equip the school community with the necessary information and knowledge in the maintenance of a healthy school environment.

Keywords: environment, knowledge, sanitation, teachers